

Advancements in Aerospace Propulsion: Thermal Efficiency, Propulsion Systems, and Sustainable Aviation Fuels

Abstract

This research paper aims to evaluate how researchers optimize propulsion system for aerospace applications, focusing on rocket nozzle design, deep-space electric propulsion systems for aerospace applications, focusing on rocket nozzle design, deep-space electric propulsion, turbine thermal efficiency, hypersonic engines, and low-emission aviation technologies. This paper explores how geometrically optimized materials such as columbian carbide-tungsten can withstand extreme temperatures exceeding 3,300 K and pressures of 6 MPa. Additionally, this study examines electric propulsion systems, including ion thrusters and nuclear-electric propulsion, highlighting their HIGH specific impulses and low thrust for extended deep-space missions. The paper also discussed thermal efficiency improvements in gas turbines, including turbine inlet optimization, heat recovery, and the use of Sustainable Aviation Fuels (SAFs) to reduce emission and improve long-term stability. Furthermore, hypersonic propulsion systems and combined-cycle engines are analyzed to understand the challenges of supersonic combustion, inlet compression, and nozzle expansion at Mach 5+ velocities. Finally, low-emission aviation technologies, integrating SAFs, operational optimizations, and advanced propulsion designs, are assessed for their role in sustainable aerospace development. Overall, the research synthesizes findings across multiple studies to provide a comprehensive evaluation of strategies that enhance performance, efficiency, and environmental sustainability in modern aerospace engineering.

Introduction

Early propulsion technologies like chemical rocket engines that were developed during the early to mid-20th century heavily focused on sufficient thrust that could overcome the Earth's gravitational forces. However, as research continued to lead to scientific advancements, the nozzle design, combustion stability as well as material science developed engines that can withstand extreme conditions that exceed 3300 K and pressures above 6 MPa. In the late 20th and early 21st centuries, electric propulsion systems were devised, specifically like ion and Hall-effect thrusters. And more recently, hypersonic propulsion systems like scramjets and combined-cycle engines were introduced to the market, which have solidified the definition behind aerodynamics, thermodynamics as well as materials engineering. Most recently, Sustainable Aviation Fuels (SAFs) emerged as a recent development in the space of aerospace propulsion, enabling the sustainable development within aviation. By the 2010s, SAF pathways like Hydroprocessed Esters and Fatty Acids (HEFA) were commercialized for aviation usage,

which further drove the direction of feedstock diversification where waste-based and power-to-liquid fuels have been leveraged to expand the SAF production process.

Optimization of Rocket Engines (Analysis of Combustion Stability, Nozzle Design)

One research study examined nozzle design optimization under specific launch conditions, utilizing mathematical techniques such as interpolation, extrapolation and other methods to create design parameters (Solomon, 2020). Additionally materials selection was evaluated based on factors including thermal stress resistance and erosion characteristics. The specific conditions were launched at 6,893ft and atmospheric pressure of 1.012 bar. The results indicate that an optimal expansion rate (A_e/A_t) of 8 provided maximum efficiency while it was maintained in safe operating conditions without flow separation. The designed nozzle achieved a thrust approximate 60kN with a mass flow rate of 24kg/s, an exhaust velocity ranging from 2,200-2,500 m/s and chamber pressures reaching of 6.66 MPa and temperatures exceeding 3,300 K (Solomon et al., 2020). Material selection was also evaluated based on thermal resistance to thermal stress and erosion, with columbium carbide-tungsten demonstrating superior performance under extreme temperatures ranging from 2,760K to over 3,500K. In another research, they review advancements in bell nozzle geometry, thermal characteristics, and materials for high performing rocket propulsion. Emphasis was placed on nozzle contour optimization, including high-angle expansion segments, parabolic exit cones, and dual-bell designs, which improve axial velocity specific impulse, and minimize oblique shocks. (Guram et al., 2022) Also thermal management strategies, such as film cooling and secondary flow injection, are evaluated for their effectiveness in reducing wall temperatures and mitigating thermal stress. The bell nozzle analyzed in this review features a throat diameter of 50mm, a cone inflection angle of 16 degrees, and achieves an exit mach number of 5.021 with an area ratio of 16. Thermal analysis considers heat-resistant steel with a thermal conductivity of $19 \text{ Wm}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ and a radial thermocouple spacing of 2mm, while flow intake conditions are 2842 K and 40 bar (Guram et al., 2022). Overall, these studies demonstrate that precise geometric optimization, material selection, and thermal management are critical for maximizing nozzle performance and efficiency. The data suggest that even small adjustments in expansion ratios, throat diameters, or secondary flow injection locations can significantly impact thrust, wall heat flux, and flow stability. Consequently, integrating advanced computational simulations with experimental validation provides a robust framework for designing new-gen rocket nozzles that are capable of higher performance, improved reliability and reduced thermal and mechanical risks under extreme operating conditions.

Chamber pressure(psia)	1500	1000	750	500	200
Chamber pressure (atm) or pressure ratio p1/p2	102.07	68.046	51.034	34.023	13.609
Chamber temperature(K)	3346.9	3322.7	3304.2	3276.6	3207.7
Nozzle exit temperature (K)	2007.7	2135.6	2226.8	2327.0	2433.6
Chamber enthalpy(cal/g)	-572.17	-572.17	-572.17	-572.17	-572.17
Exit enthalpy(cal/g)	-1382.19	-1325.15	-1282.42	-1219.8	-1071.2
Entropy((cal/g-K)	2.1826	2.2101	2.2597	2.2574	2.320
Chamber molecular mass(kg/mol)	29.303	29.215	29.149	29.050	28.908
Exit molecular mass(kg/mol)	29.879	29.853	29.820	29.763	29.668
Exit Mach number	3.20	3.00	2.86	2.89	2.32
Specific heat ratio-chamber, K	1.1369	1.1351	1.1337	1.1318	1.1272
Specific impulse, vacuum (sec)	287.4	280.1	274.6	265.7	242.4
Specific impulse, sea level expansion (sec)	265.5	256.0	248.6	237.3	208.4
Characteristic velocity c* (m/sec)	1532	1529	1527	1525	1517
Nozzle area ration, A_2/A_t^a	14.297	10.541	8.507	8.531	6.300
Thrust coefficient, c_f^a	1.700	1.641	1.596	1.597	1.529

(Figure 1: Performance Characteristics of Rocket Nozzle Flow at Varying Chamber Pressures and Expansion Conditions)

In accordance with the graph above, this figure shows the different composites and how they are affected by different chamber pressures. Figure 1 presents the performance characteristics of a rocket nozzle using aluminized ammonium perchlorate propellant across a range of chamber pressure from 200 psia to 1500 psia. The data clearly shows how nozzle performance varies with operating conditions, supporting the discussion of nozzle optimization in the paragraph. The data highlights that increasing chamber pressure generally improves the thrust and efficiency, with the exit Mach number rising from 2.32 to 3.20 and the nozzle area approaching 8-14.

Analysis of High-Efficiency Propulsion for Deep-Space Missions

Researchers are evaluating electric propulsion systems as the most efficient option for deep-space missions, particularly due to their prominent features like high specific impulse, long operational life as well as their ability to enable complex space missions (Randolph, 2017). Hence, propulsion systems are able to leverage electric energy to accelerate ions, which are plasma. While they are able to only produce very low thrust, they possess very high efficiency and high specific impulse. Researchers addressed how ion thrusters are able to accelerate ions using electric fields, which are best for conducting long-duration missions and possess precise and trajectory control. In comparison to this, hall effect thrusters depend upon magnetic and electric fields, often possessing higher thrust than ion thrusters and are widely utilized in satellites for greater and more optimal communications. Systems that were analyzed as part of the studies were operating at 1-10 kW power range, as these systems are designed to foster very high total impulse over long durations (Randolph, 2017). In comparison to electric propulsion

systems that were operating at high efficiency of nearly 3000 s, chemical propulsions were coordinated at significantly lower rates. Therefore, arguably, electric propulsion systems are able to minimize propellant mass, while maximizing the mission duration. When another group of researchers examined the interventions of propulsion systems for deep-space missions, they discovered that ion thrusters are ideal for more long-duration and deep-space missions, while the NEP was more suitable for sustained propulsion over longer distances. Lastly, other groups of researchers have analyzed ion propulsion in deep-space missions, especially NASA's Dawn mission in proposing an optimized propulsion system. When conducting studies, they uncovered that ion propulsion systems were able to achieve specific impulses of 3100-4000 seconds while operating at lower thrust levels of 90 to 240 mN, which was able to enable the spacecraft to reach delta-V values that exceeded 11km over longer durations (Singh, 2025). These empirical studies have significant implications for future deep-space missions, as these results help to enable the spacecraft to reduce propellant mass while extending the operational duration, which can subsequently shape the payload capacity and mission flexibility.

Interventions of Thermal Efficiency in Turbines and Aviation Fuels (SAF)

Regarding the thermal efficiency of a gas turbine cycle, researchers found that increasing the turbine inlet temperature was able to lead to greater efficiency. However, this was only the case for up to an optimal point where material and cooling limitations began to offset its gains. Specifically, researchers saw that for typical simple-cycle gas turbines, the efficiencies were able to rise to approximately 35-40%, while on the other hand, advanced systems are able to reach up to 45-46% under more optimized and controlled conditions (Kurzke, 2003).

Composition		
Aromatics, vol %	25	Max
Sulfur, total, wt %	0.30	Max
Volatility		
10% recovered distillation temperature °C	205	Max
Final Boiling point °C	300	Max
Flash point °C	38	Min
Density at 15°C	775-840	
Fluidity		
Freezing point °C	-40	Max
Viscosity at -20°C, cSt	8.0	Max
Combustion		
Net heat of Combustion, MJ/kg	42.8	Min
Smoke point, mm	25	Min
Corrosion		
Copper strip, 2h at 100°C	No. 1	Max
Stability		
Tube deposit rating	<3, no peacock or abnormal-colored deposits	
Additives		
Electrical conductivity, pS/m	50-600	

(Figure 2: Composition, Volatility, Fluidity, Combustion, Corrosion, Stability and Additives)

As evident in the figure above, conventional Jet-A standards are not optimized for maximum thermal efficiency. In this figure above, data points show how there are upper limits for aromatics of 25% and sulfur (0.30 wt%), which indicates higher soot formation, increased radiative losses as well as greater long-term degradation. Furthermore, in conjunction with the temperature points, the compressor pressure ratio was also subsequently shaping the values with optimal values ranging between 15-30, depending on the system designs. Based on the research findings derived from Kurzke, researchers identified that cycle modifications can work in the form of cycle modifications recuperation where exhaust heat is reused, which subsequently increases efficiency intercooling, and then reduces compressor work to reheat the cycles. Furthermore, another remarkable result was that waste heat can be used to generate additional power, which can then uplift its efficiency by 60% as opposed to 35-40% for simple cycles. Overall, these results suggest that optimizing fuel-air ratio, and using heat recovery through recuperation and combined cycle can improve component efficiency. On the contrary, Sustainable Aviation Fuels (SAFs) play a significant role in enhancing the thermal efficiency of gas turbines. Researchers uncovered that fuel composition can directly affect the flame structure, heat release rates as well as chemical reaction pathways, which ultimately shape how energy is converted within the turbine. In comparison to jet fuels, SAFs are able to possess a higher hydrogen-to-carbon ratio of specifically a 1.9 as opposed to a 1.8, as well as a lower aromatic content by 50-80%, which can enable cleaner and more uniform combustion (Kurzke, 2003). Nonetheless, SAFs can provide great impact, which can deliver CO₂ emissions by approximately 60-80%, and lead to greater long-term performance stability and environmental efficiency through cleaner combustion and reduced degradation.

Analysis of Hypersonic and Advanced Propulsion Systems

In this study it examined hypersonic propulsion systems, particular scramjet-based engines, emphasizing their performance across varying Mach regimes and their integration with vehicle design. Researchers found that as flight speed increased beyond Mach 5, scramjets became more efficient than traditional ramjets due to their ability to sustain supersonic combustion, while rockets, although less efficient, remained essential for operation beyond the atmosphere (Segal, 2004). The analysis showed that the scramjet performance was highly dependent on managing the kinetic energy of incoming airflow, as at extreme velocities, the airstream energy significantly exceeded the energy added through combustion. This required precise optimization of inlet compression, combustion efficiency, and nozzle expansion to maintain thrust generation. Additionally, studies indicated that combined-cycle propulsion systems, such as turbine-based and rocket-based combined cycles, were necessary to enable efficient operation across a broad flight envelope. These systems transitioned between modes (turbojet, ramjet, scramjet, and

rocket) depending on altitude and speed, improving overall specific and mission flexibility. Quantitative findings showed that dynamic pressure constraints for hypersonic vehicles ranged between 4500-9000 kg/m² (Segal, 2004), balancing aerodynamic drag and structural limits. Furthermore, propulsion efficiency was strongly influenced by component efficiencies; including compression, combustion, and expansion processes, with small inefficiencies significantly reducing overall performance. The *Hypersonic Airbreathing Propulsion* article by Van Wie et al. (2005) provides an in-depth examination of the challenges and performance considerations associated with high-speed airbreathing engine systems. The authors emphasize that engine performance is strongly influenced by component geometry, thermodynamics behaviour, and materials capable of withstanding extreme aerothermal loads.

Low-Emission Aviation Technologies for Sustainable Development

In the development of low-emission aviation technologies, an optimal strategy incorporates fuel innovation, engine efficiency and operational improvements. In order to create a sustainable and low-emission technology, it is crucial to incorporate aerodynamics, lightweight materials, optimized flight operations as well as an advanced propulsion system that can align better with ESG sustainable metrics. Out of all aviation technologies, researchers identified SAFs as one of the most impactful solutions in terms of sustainability as they can deliver substantial lifecycle CO₂ reductions of up to 80% depending on feedstock and production pathways. Researchers argue that in order to bridge this gap, it is crucial to create low-emission technologies, where SAF can provide immediate emission reductions while technological innovations can drive long-term efficiency gains as well as a system-wide decarbonization (Lee et al., 2017). Other researchers highlighted how alternative fuels, including biofuels and synthetic fuels are able to lower the CO₂ emissions by enabling cleaner combustion, which can thus, improve thermal efficiency by reducing the heat losses and engine fouling (Agrawal, 2012). Furthermore, the Advisory Committee for Aeronautical Research in Europe (ACARE) established goals to meet sustainable metrics, by reducing the perceived noise to one half current average levels, as well as reducing the CO₂ emissions by 50%, and the NO_x emissions by 80% relative to the 2000's.

(Figure 5: Chart Showing CO2 Emissions and Carbon Neutral Timeline)

The figure above represents how aviation emissions can be reduced over time, highlighting how sustainable development in aviation relies upon multiple low-emission technologies. For instance, this diagram above highlights how the incremental improvements from aircrafts, such as the enhancements in turbine thermal efficiency (represented by ERA technology only play a minor role. On the contrary, the largest reduction is attributed to the development of alternative fuels, particularly Sustainable Aviation Fuels (SAFs), which form the most substantial portion of the emissions reduction by 2050. In conclusion, the integrative approach of combining turbine efficiency, operational optimization as well as SAF adoption can work in synergy, in order to create more sustainable change within the aviation industry.

Ethics, Discussion, Limitations

While the development of advanced propulsion systems and low-emission aviation technologies are crucial in the scientific paradigm, it is also important to consider some of the ethical considerations and limitations. When researchers maximize efficiency, thrust and performance, this can lead to high temperatures which exceed 3,300K as well as pressures above 6MPa, which require the use of rare, high-performance materials and energy-intensive testing processes. Thus, these challenges can lead to environmental risks regarding material extraction and manufacturing, as well as the implications on long-term sustainability. However, what is most important to acknowledge is that Sustainable Aviation Fuels (SAFs) have been introduced to the market as a critical method to reduce lifecycle CO2 emissions by 60-80%, highlighting their

environmental efficacies. Additionally, the high cost as well as the limited scalability of SAF technologies has also raised concerns about unequal access, where only specific developed regions or major airlines could implement these solutions. It is also crucial to consider that for SAF technologies, their reliance on biomass as well as synthetic feedstocks have led to open discussions and concerns regarding land use competition, biodiversity loss as well as food security. For worldwide governance, it is also imperative to consider the dual-use nature of advanced propulsion systems, particularly hypersonic technologies, as they require careful governance and international oversight in managing. Therefore, for research in the future, researchers must ensure greater stewardship, equitable access, as well as long-term global accountability. For future research to maximize sustainable resources, equitable access to emerging technologies, proper governance as well as policy work would be crucial to ensure that advancements in aerospace engineering align with long-term environmental changes.

Conclusion

In conclusion, as analyzed in this research publication, from rocket nozzle optimization to deep space ion propulsion systems, maximizing performance within this industry requires a highly integrated approach that involves geometry optimization, material selection, as well as advanced fuel systems. With the rocket nozzles, it was uncovered that a precise control over the expansion ratios, chamber pressures and thermal management can significantly improve the thrust and stability under extreme conditions, which can exceed 3,300K and 6 MPa. Similar to this, deep space propulsion systems were able to achieve high efficiencies ranging from 3000 to 4000 seconds, which extended the durations of missions. Specifically for aviation, the gas turbine efficiency was demonstrated to improve from approximately 35-40% in simple cycles to 45-46% in optimized systems. In accordance with sustainability metrics, incorporating Sustainable Aviation Fuels (SAFs) with a lifecycle CO₂ reduction of up to 60-80% was identified to be the most impactful application in reducing emissions, especially when paired with a solid engine design and operational optimization. However, moving forward, ethical considerations and limitations must be incorporated into future research trials, in ensuring that sustainable resources are maximized and emerging technologies are made equitable in the sector of aerospace engineering.

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